

Electronic Invoices in Europe

Between 2016 and 2021, their use grew by approximately 78.40% for DESI countries

The Desi Index calculates the value of companies that use electronic invoices for automated processing. The data are available for the period 2016-2021 for various European countries with the exclusion of the United Kingdom.

Ranking of European countries by value of electronic invoices in 2021. Italy is in first place for value of electronic invoices with a value of 9.48, followed by Finland with a value of 8.28 and Estonia with a value equal to 6.23. In the middle of the table are France with an amount of 2.33 units, followed by Malta with an amount of 2.2 units and Austria with an amount of 2,199 units. The Czech Republic closed the ranking with an amount of 1,220, Greece with an amount of 1,194 units and Bulgaria with an amount equal to 1,001. On average, the value of the use of electronic invoices in 2021 was equal to an amount of 3.006.

Ranking of European countries by percentage change in the value of electronic invoices between 2016 and 2021. Croatia is in first place by value of the percentage changes in the number of companies that use electronic invoices with an amount equal to 418.135% equal to an amount of 3.47 units, followed by Estonia with an amount equal to 302.225% equal to an amount of 4.687 units and followed by Italy with an amount equal to 236.888% equal to an amount of 6.672 units. In the middle of the table there is Slovakia with an amount equal to 58.726% or an amount equal to 0.61 units, followed by Austria with an amount equal to 58.719% equal to an amount of 0.813 units and by Germany with an amount equal to 58.29% equal to an amount of 0.652 units. Romania closes the ranking with an amount of 23.363% equal to an amount of 0.321 units, Bulgaria with an amount of 17.92% equal to an amount of 0.152 units and Portugal with an amount equal to -3.357% equal to a amount of -0.06 units. On average, the value of the changes for the Desi countries considered is equal to an amount of 87.30% in the period between 2016 and 2021 and equal to an amount of 1.32 units in absolute value.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Below is a machine learning analysis for predicting the future value of the use of electronic invoices in DESI countries. The algorithms were compared on the basis of their ability to minimize statistical errors and maximize the R-square. In addition, 80% of the data was used for the learning rate while the remaining 20% was used for the actual prediction. From the performance comparison of the algorithms the following order was obtained:

- SGD with a payoff value of 4;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 12;
- Random Forest with a payoff value of 14;
- kNN with a payoff value of 15;
- SVM and Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 19;
- Tree c Costant with a payoff value of 20;
- AdaBoost with a payoff value of 25;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 28.

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and researcher in Economics at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

Therefore, using the SGD algorithm it is possible to predict the amount of the future value of the use of electronic invoices. In particular, there are two types of countries: winners countries and losers countries. Winner countries are those for which an increase in the value of the use of electronic invoices is expected. Losers countries are those for which a reduction in the value of the use of electronic invoices is expected. Among the winners countries are the following:

- Portugal with an increase from an amount of 1.74 up to a value of 3.22 units or a change equal to an amount of 1.48 units equivalent to an amount of 85.28%;
- Bulgaria with an increase from an amount of 1.00 units up to a value of 1.81 units or equal to a variation of 0.81 units equal to an amount of 80.56%;
- Czech Republic with an increase from an amount of 1.22 units up to a value of 2.00 units or a change equal to an amount of 0.78 units equivalent to a value of 63.62%;
- Poland with an increase from an amount of 1.32 units up to a value of 2.12 units or equal to a variation of 0.79 units equivalent to an amount of 60.07%;
- Romania with an increase from an amount of 1.69 units up to a value of 2.68 units or equal to a change of 0.98 units equal to an amount of 58.08%;
- Luxembourg with an increase from an amount of 1.36 units up to an amount of 2.15 units or equal to a change of 0.78 units or equal to an amount of 57.38%;
- Ireland with an increase from an amount of 1.87 units up to a value of 2.48 units or equal to an amount of 0.61 units equal to a variation of 32.74%;
- France with an increase from an amount of 2.34 units up to a value of 3.09 units or equal to a variation of 0.75 units equal to an amount of 32.28%;
- Lithuania with an increase from an amount of 2.67 units up to a value of 3.49 units or equal to an amount of 0.83 units equal to a value of 30.92%;
- Cyprus with an increase from an amount of 1.31 units up to a value of 1.7 units or equal to a variation of 0.4 units equal to an amount of 30.61%;
- Greece with an increase from an amount of 1.19 units up to a value of 1.5 units or equal to a value of 0.31 units equal to a value of 25.88%;
- Slovakia with an increase from an amount of 1.65 units up to a value of 2.03 units or equal to a change of 2.03 units or equal to a value of 0.38 units equal to an amount of 22, 86%;
- Germany with an increase from an amount of 1.77 units up to a value of 2.11 units or equal to a variation of 0.34 units equal to an amount of 19.00%;
- Slovenia with an increase from an amount of 5.84 units up to an amount of 6.83 units or equal to an amount of 0.99 units equal to a value of 17.04%;
- Spain with a variation from an amount of 3.28 units up to a value of 3.81 units or equal to a variation of 0.52 units equal to an amount of 15.86%;
- Austria with a variation from an amount of 2.2 units up to a value of 2.53 units or equal to a variation of 0.33 units equal to an amount of 15.05%;
- Denmark with a variation from an amount of 5.73 units up to a value of 6.31 units or equal to a variation of 0.57 units equal to a value of 9.97%;
- Hungary with an increase from an amount of 1.35 units up to a value of 1.46 units or equal to a variation of 0.11 units equal to an amount of 7.81%;
- Finland with a variation from an amount of 8.29 units up to a value of 8.88 units or equal to a variation of 0.6 units equal to an amount of 7.21%;
- Belgium with a variation from an amount of 2.46 units up to a value of 2.59 units or equal to an amount of 0.13 units equal to an amount of 5.26%;
- the Netherlands with a variation from an amount of 2.56 units up to a value of 2.68 units or equal to a variation of 0.13 units equal to an amount of 4.96%;

- Malta with a variation from an amount of 2.25 units up to a value of 2.3 units or equal to a variation of 0.05 units equal to an amount of 2.26%.

In addition, the algorithm also predicts the countries in which there will be a reduction in the use of electronic invoices, namely:

- Sweden with a variation from an amount of 4.54 units up to a value of 4.15 units or equal to a variation of -0.39 units equal to an amount of -8.63%;
- Latvia with a variation from an amount of 1.49 units up to a value of 1.18 units or equal to a variation of -0.31 units equal to an amount of -20.72%;
- Italy with a variation from 9.49 units up to a value of 4.37 units or equal to a variation of -5.12 units equal to a variation of -53.98%;
- Estonia with a variation from an amount of 6.24 units up to a value of 2.64 units or equal to an amount of -3.6 units equal to an amount of -57.66%;
- Croatia with a variation from an amount of 4.3 units up to a value of 1.53 units or equal to a variation of -2.77 units equal to an amount of -64.52%.

Conclusions. The use of electronic invoices grew by about 78% on average between 2014 and 2021 for the DESI countries. However, despite significant growth, there are still many countries in which the use of electronic invoices is still not widespread. Electronic invoices are necessary, both for issues related to tax security and also for reasons relating to the efficiency of the internal management systems of companies. In this regard, it should be considered that electronic invoices are also more in line with the objectives of combating tax evasion and can also facilitate taxpayers' obligations.

Declarations

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